

Molecular mechanisms of action and resistance to the first-line drugs against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

Md Zahid Hasan¹, Maysha Fahmeda Priota¹, Md Mosabbir Hossain¹, Md Maruf Chowdhury¹, Debobrata Sharma², Fateama Sikdhar², B.M. Mahmudul Hasan^{*3}, Md Mahmudul Islam⁴

¹Department of Microbiology, Rajshahi Institute of Biosciences,
Affiliated with University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi, Bangladesh

²Department of Pharmacy, University of Development Alternative, Bangladesh

³Department of Public Health Nutrition, Primeasia University, Bangladesh

⁴Department of Microbiology, Shaheed Shamsuzzoha Institute of Biosciences,
Affiliated with University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Key words: Tuberculosis, Infectious, Drug resistance, Therapy, Mechanisms, First-line drugs

<http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/24.5.38-49>

Article published on May 03, 2024

Abstract

Tuberculosis, caused by the infectious pathogenic bacteria *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, is one of the top 10 infectious agents (above AIDS/HIV) that cause death globally, and a large number of people contract the disease every year. Significantly, the four first-line drugs (rifampicin, isoniazid, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol) that make up the foundation of treatment regimens throughout the first six to nine months of treatment are delivered in various combinations when administering TB treatments. It is very important to continuously update information on molecular mechanisms of action and resistance to the anti-tuberculosis drugs against *M. tuberculosis* due the global rises in 558 000 new cases of rifampicin-resistant/ multidrug-resistant tuberculosis recently. In many countries and regions, even more severe cases of drug resistance have been documented in recent years. The aim of this review is to provide an overview of the latest report on molecular mechanisms of action and resistance to the first-line drugs against *M. tuberculosis*. A better knowledge of the mechanisms of action and resistance of anti-tuberculosis drugs would be very helpful for efficient tuberculosis therapy and clinical care.

* Corresponding Author: B. M. Mahmudul Hasan ✉ jewelgono@gmail.com

Introduction

Tuberculosis is a communicable disease and one of the top ten causes of death worldwide from a single infectious agent (above AIDS/HIV) and a lot of people fall sick with the TB disease each year (Bu *et al.*, 2022; Islam *et al.*, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic is still having a negative effect on the burden of tuberculosis disease and the availability of tuberculosis diagnosis and treatment. Global tuberculosis targets are not being met, and progress gained in the years leading up to 2019 has slowed, halted, or reversed. Globally, there is an estimate that 10.6 million people have developed tuberculosis disease by the year 2021, a rise of 4.5% from 10.1 million in 2020 (WHO, 2022). According to estimates, the number of new cases of drug-resistant tuberculosis increased from 2020 to 2021, accounting for 450 000 cases of rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis in 2021. Geographically, the Western Pacific (18%), Africa (23%) and South-East Asia (45%) areas of the World Health Organization (WHO) had the highest percentage of tuberculosis cases in 2021 (18%), followed by the Eastern Mediterranean (8.1%), the Americas (2.9%) and Europe (2.2%). 87% of the estimated incident cases worldwide were from the 30 countries with the highest tuberculosis burdens (WHO, 2022). More than two thirds of the world's total came from eight of these nations, including Nigeria (4.4%), Bangladesh (3.6%), Pakistan (5.7%), the Philippines (7.0%), and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (2.9%).

Drug-resistant tuberculosis is still a danger issue to public health (Boshoff *et al.*, 2023). Almost all existing antibiotics are no longer as effective against *M. tuberculosis* due to the rising incidence of drug resistance in this disease, which makes efforts to stop its spread worldwide more difficult (Waller *et al.*, 2023). The major worry is resistance to rifampicin, the most efficient first-line treatment (Prasad *et al.*, 2018). Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is described as having resistance to rifampicin and isoniazid. Rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis both need to be treated with second-line drugs. Between 2015 and

2020, the predicted annual number of people who developed multidrug-resistant tuberculosis or rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis was largely steady, but it increased in 2021 (WHO, 2022). A projected 450 000 incident cases were reported in 2021, an increase of 3.1% from the 437 000 reported in 2020. Multidrug-/rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis were expected to account for 3.6% of new cases and 18% of those that had previously been treated in tuberculosis in 2021; in 2015, the corresponding numbers were 3.9% and 20%. 26% of cases worldwide in 2021 were in India, 8.5% were in the Russian Federation, and 7.9% were in Pakistan (WHO, 2022). These three nations accounted for 42% of all cases worldwide. The COVID-19 pandemic's effects on tuberculosis detection are thought to be the primary reason for the overall rise in tuberculosis incidence between 2020 and 2021, which is the key explanation for the rise (WHO, 2022).

Immune system of human body can't stop growing of bacteria, when *M. tuberculosis* becomes active form, this is called tuberculosis disease (Miggiano *et al.*, 2020). It is very significant that persons who have tuberculosis disease are treated by several drugs for six to nine months. More than twenty drugs have been introduced for the treatment of tuberculosis until now. These drugs have been divided into first-line drugs and second line drugs, and have been categorized into five different groups by the WHO.

The anti-tuberculosis drugs isoniazid, rifampicin, streptomycin, ethambutol and pyrazinamide are collectively called the first-line drugs. In general, the first-line drugs have the significant activity against drug-susceptible tuberculosis (Dartois and Rubin, 2022). These drugs are the core component of tuberculosis control problem worldwide. In fact, isoniazid and rifampicin drugs are still the cornerstones for treating in drug-susceptible tuberculosis (Stenkens *et al.*, 2023). Both drugs are available and cheap worldwide. The aim of this review is to provide an overview of the latest report on molecular mechanisms of action and resistance to the first-line drugs against *M. tuberculosis*.

Mechanisms of action and resistance to first-line drugs

Drug sensitive disease is treated effectively by using first-line drugs: isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, ethambutol and streptomycin. However, the continuation phase of the tuberculosis treatment is very important to kill slow growing strains of *M. tuberculosis*. The WHO recommends that drug sensitive tuberculosis patient has to take tuberculosis drug treatment more than six months including a two month intensive treatment phase followed by a continuation phase of four or seven months. Sometimes, the first-line drugs treatment can fail to cure tuberculosis for several factors. Anti-tuberculosis drugs resistance arise primarily due to inappropriate treatment regimens, previous use of anti-tuberculosis drugs, primary infection with drug-resistant strains, and poor adherence to regulated treatment (Gandhi *et al.*, 2010; Dheda *et al.*, 2014). Mechanisms of drug resistance of first- and second-line drugs are presented in Table 1. First-line anti-tuberculosis drugs are isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, ethambutol and streptomycin and second-line anti-tuberculosis drugs are ofloxacin, levofloxacin, moxifloxacin, ciprofloxacin, kanamycin, amikacin, capreomycin, ethionamide/prothionamide, cycloserine/terizidone, p-aminosalicylic acid.

Isoniazid

One of the most important first-line drugs for treating both the conventional treatment regimen and drug sensitive *M. tuberculosis* strains is isoniazid (Mitchison, 1985). In 1952, isoniazid was first offered as an anti-tuberculosis drug (Fox, 1952). Isoniazid does not work against non-growing bacilli; it is only effective against *M. tuberculosis* that is growing (Zhang *et al.*, 1992). Like other tuberculosis drugs, pyrazinamide, ethionamide, and prothionamide, isoniazid is a pro-drug that needs to be activated by the catalase/oxidase enzyme that is encoded by the *katG* gene (Zhang *et al.*, 1992). A hypothetical isonicotinoyl anion or radical is formed when the catalase/oxidase enzyme activates INH (Zhang *et al.*, 1992; Lei *et al.*, 2000). When this substance combines with NAD⁺, an INH-NAD adduct is created

that binds. There are two main ways that the fundamental mechanisms of isoniazid resistance might occur. First, mutations in the *katG* gene or in the regulator region can be used to block the activation of the isoniazid medication (Vilchèze and Jacobs, 2014). For example, up to 97.5% of clinical isolates of *M. tuberculosis* that is resistant to isoniazid had the *katG* gene mutation S315 (Kiepiela *et al.*, 2000). Worldwide, mutations in the *katG* gene, primarily the S315T alteration, have been most commonly associated with INH resistance. Second, mutations in the *inhA* gene or its promoter region can circumvent the inhibition of *InhA* by the isoniazid-NAD adduct (Vilchèze and Jacobs, 2014). The most common mutations after *katG* gene mutations are found in the *mabA-inhA* regulatory region. Significantly, two of the most prevalent variants are *inhA-15*, which results in low-level INH resistance, and *katG 315*, which results in high-level INH resistance (Zenteno-Cuevas *et al.*, 2019; Hsu *et al.*, 2023; Khan *et al.*, 2023). However, it has not yet been shown that mutations in the *oxyR-ahpC* area directly confer INH resistance (Kandler *et al.*, 2018; Hsu *et al.*, 2023).

Rifampicin

One of the most effective first-line anti-tuberculosis drugs is rifampicin, which also acts as a surrogate marker for the identification of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (Sinha *et al.*, 2020). Rifampicin has very good sterilizing properties and was first commercialized in 1972 as an anti-tuberculosis antibiotic. Rifampicin inhibits bacterial transcription activity by binding to the β -subunit of RNA polymerase (*rpoB*) (Ramaswamy and Musser, 1998), the enzyme responsible for mycobacterial gene transcription and expression. This ultimately leads to the organism's death. Rifampicin's ability to effectively inhibit both actively developing and slowly metabolizing (non-growing) bacilli is a crucial feature (Mitchison, 1979). Adverse responses to RIF are comparatively rare. It might irritate someone's stomach. Compared to the administration of isoniazid, hepatotoxicity is less common. Treating tuberculosis is hampered by the rapid identification

of genes linked to rifampicin resistance in *Mtb* strains. The primary cause of *Mtb* resistance to rifampicin drug is mutations of the *rpoB* gene (Lai *et al.*, 2002; Zaczek *et al.*, 2009). Research has demonstrated that rifampicin resistance emerges infrequently in comparison to other anti-tuberculosis drugs, and approximately 90% of cases resistant to rifampicin drug are also resistant to isoniazid drug (Farooqi *et al.*, 2012). Genetic alterations in the *rpoB* gene are present in over 90% of clinical cases of rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis, and over 80% of these cases are multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (Huang *et al.*, 2018; Jagielski *et al.*, 2018). Of note, mutations in an 81-bp segment of the *rpoB* gene, which is situated in *Mtb* between *rpoB* codons 426 and 452, are mostly linked to rifampicin resistance (Jagielski *et al.*, 2018; Zaw *et al.*, 2018). Another recent study reported that 98.06% of the rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis cases contained the *rpoB* gene alterations, and 47.57% of them were resistant to both rifampicin and isoniazid at the same time (Zenget *et al.*, 2021). Though the resistance mechanism for the remaining 5% of rifampicin-resistant isolates is still unknown, it's possible that there are alternative mechanisms at play, such as increased efflux pump activity or decreased cell wall permeability (Xu *et al.*, 2021).

Streptomycin

In 1942, the first utilized as first-line drug to treat tuberculosis cases was streptomycin, an aminocyclitol drug, along with the four other drugs in the regimen includes rifampicin, isoniazid, ethambutol and pyrazinamide. Following the discovery of the streptomycin drug, it was used as tuberculosis monotherapy, which quickly caused streptomycin-resistant strains to become resistant. While streptomycin is inactive against non-growing tubercle bacilli, it destroys those that grow slowly. Mutations in the *rpsL* gene (Rv0682) and the *rrs* gene (Rvn01), which are encoding for the 16S rRNA and the ribosomal protein S12, respectively, have been linked to streptomycin resistance (Nahid *et al.*, 2019; Cohen *et al.*, 2020; Jia *et al.*, 2021; Shafipouret *et al.*, 2022). The majority of chromosomal alterations are that cause

streptomycin resistance. Intermediate or higher levels of streptomycin resistance have been associated with mutations in the *rpsL* or *rrs* genes (Nahid *et al.*, 2019; Cohen *et al.*, 2020; Jia *et al.*, 2021). Depending on the population and geographic area, different STR resistance related mutations have different types and frequencies. Nonetheless, a number of studies revealed that the prevalence of mutations varies from 37.7% to 94.6% depending on the nation (Cohen *et al.*, 2020; Jia *et al.*, 2021; Shafipouret *et al.*, 2022). In STR-resistant *M. tuberculosis* isolates, the most notable alterations are located in the *rpsL* gene at codons 43 and 88 (Nahid *et al.*, 2019; Cohen *et al.*, 2020; Jia *et al.*, 2021; Shafipouret *et al.*, 2022). In STR-resistant *M. tuberculosis* isolates, the most prevalent mutations in the *rrs* gene are found at many locations, including 513, 514, 517, 905, 906, 907, 908, and 1401 (Nahid *et al.*, 2019).

The *gidB* (*Rv3919c*) gene has been shown to encode a 7-methylguanosine (m7G) methyltransferase that is dependent on S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) and that methylates the G527 in the 530 loop of the 16S rRNA. High-performance liquid chromatography analysis of 16S rRNA revealed that the *gidB* mutant lacked an m7G alteration, which was linked to resistance to STR (Rodríguez-García *et al.*, 2021). Interestingly, non-synonymous mutations in *gidB* typically correspond to low resistance values (Jia *et al.*, 2021; Shafipouret *et al.*, 2022).

Pyrazinamide

One of the cornerstone drugs for the treatment of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is pyrazinamide, a significant first-line anti-tuberculosis drug used in short-course chemotherapy (Mitchison, 1985). PZA, a prodrug and structural analogue of nicotinamide, must be transformed by the non-essential enzyme pyrazinamidase, which is encoded by the *pncA* gene, into pyrazinoic acid (POA). Both the function of membrane transporters and membrane energetics are disrupted by pyrazinoic acid. Numerous genes, including *pncA*, *panD*, *rpsA*, *clpC*, and the putative efflux pumps *Rv3756c*, *Rv0191*, *Rv1667c*, and *Rv3008* have been associated to PZA resistance;

nevertheless, *pncA* mutations are highly associated with PZA resistance and account for the majority of PZA resistance cases (70–97%) throughout the entire coding region of *pncA* gene. Up to 20% of non-multi-

drug resistant tuberculosis patients have PZA resistance, indicating that resistance has been greatly underestimated despite the critical role PZA plays in clinical outcomes (Juma *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1. Genes involved in mechanisms of action and resistance to the first-line and second-line drugs in *M.tuberculosis*.

Drugs	Gene involved in resistance	Role of gene product	Resistance mechanism of action	Reference
Isoniazid	<i>katG</i>	Catalase-peroxidase	Inhibits of mycolic acid synthesis and other effects	Banerjee <i>et al.</i> , 1994; Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 1992; Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 1996; Mdluliet <i>et al.</i> , 1998 ; Parish <i>et al.</i> , 2007
	<i>inhA</i>	Enoyl ACP reductase		
	<i>ahpC</i>	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase		
	<i>fabG1</i>	3-Oxoacyl (acyl-carrier protein) reductases		
	<i>iniA</i>	Efflux pump associated		
	<i>fadE24</i>	Involved in fatty acid β -oxidation		
	<i>kasA</i>	Ketoacyl acyl carrier protein synthase		
Rifampicin	<i>ndh</i>	NADH dehydrogenase	Inhibits of RNA synthesis	Telentiet <i>et al.</i> , 1993; Comas <i>et al.</i> , 2012
	<i>rpoB</i>	β -subunit of RNA polymerase		
	<i>rpoA</i>	α -subunit of RNA polymerase		
Pyrazinamide	<i>rpoC</i>	β' -subunit of RNA polymerase	Inhibits of trans-translation and pantothenate and CoA synthesis	Scorpio and Zhang, 1996; Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2013
	<i>pncA</i>	PZase		
	<i>rpsA</i>	Ribosomal S1 protein		
Streptomycin	<i>panD</i>	Aspartate decarboxylase	Inhibits of protein synthesis	Nair <i>et al.</i> , 1993; Okamoto <i>et al.</i> , 2007
	<i>rpsL</i>	S12 ribosomal protein		
	<i>rrs</i>	16S rRNA		
Ethambutol	<i>gidB</i>	7-methylguanosine methyltransferase	Inhibits of arabinogalactan synthesis	Telentiet <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Safi <i>et al.</i> , 2013
	<i>embB</i>	Arabinosyl transferase		
	<i>embA</i>	Arabinosyl transferase		
	<i>embC</i>	Arabinosyl transferase		
	<i>embR</i>	Regulator of embCAB operon expression		
Fluoroquinolone	<i>rmlD</i>	dTDP-4-dehydrorhamnose reductase	Inhibition of DNA synthesis	Ginsburg <i>et al.</i> 2003 ; Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2005
	<i>ubiA</i>	DPPR synthase		
	<i>gyrA</i>	DNA gyrase subunit A		
kanamycin / amikacin	<i>gyrB</i>	DNA gyrase subunit B	Inhibits of protein synthesis	Alangadenet <i>et al.</i> , 1998; Reeves <i>et al.</i> , 2013
	<i>rrs</i>	16S rRNA		
	<i>eis</i>	Aminoglycoside acetyltransferase		
Capreomycin / viomycin	<i>whiB7</i>	Transcriptional regulator	Inhibits of protein synthesis	Maus <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Johansen <i>et al.</i> , 2006
	<i>thyA</i>	rRNA methyltransferase		
Ethionamide/ Prothionamide	<i>rrs</i>	16S rRNA	Disrupts cell wall biosynthesis	Baulardet <i>et al.</i> , 2000
	<i>inhA</i>	Fatty acid enoyl acyl carrier protein reductase A		
	<i>ethA</i>	Flavin monooxygenase		
Para-aminosalicylic acid	<i>ethR</i>	Transcriptional repressor	Inhibits of folic acid and thymine nucleotide metabolism	Rengarajan <i>et al.</i> , 2004
	<i>thyA</i>	Thymidylate synthase A		
	<i>folC</i>	Dihydrofolate synthase		
	<i>dfrA</i>	Dihydrofolate reductase		
D-cycloserine	<i>ribD</i>	Riboflavin biosynthesis	Inhibits the synthesis of peptidoglycan in the cell wall	Caceres <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Bruninget <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Saieret <i>et al.</i> , 2009
	<i>alr</i>	D-alanine racemase		
	<i>ddl</i>	D-alanine: D-alanine ligase		
	<i>ald</i>	L-alanine dehydrogenase		
Clofazimine	<i>CycA</i>	D-serine proton symporter	Produces of reactive oxygen species, inhibits of energy production	Milano <i>et al.</i> , 2009 ; Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2015
	<i>Rv0678</i>	Transcription repressor for efflux pump		
	<i>MmpL5</i>	MmpL5		
	<i>rv1979c</i>	Unknown		
	<i>rv2535c</i>	Unknown		

ACP = acyl-carrier-protein; NADH = Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide; CoA = coenzyme A; DPPR = 5-phospho-a-d-ribose-1-diphosphate: decaprenyl-phosphate 5-phosphoribosyltransferase.

The most frequent causes of pyrazinamide resistance in *M. tuberculosis* are mutations in the *pncA* gene or its promoter region, which lowers PZase activity (Mok *et al.*, 2021). It is very significant to note that whole

genome sequencing may help identify pyrazinamide resistance because it will be difficult to build a quick molecular drug susceptibility screening due to the distributed nature of mutations throughout the entire

pncA gene. A very recent study reported that PZA resistance has increased recently among MDR-TB cases (55% to 58%), which emphasizes the need for the development of both conventional and innovative treatment regimens (Wang *et al.*, 2023).

Ethambutol

One crucial first-line anti-TB drug for treating drug-susceptible tuberculosis and halting the development of treatment resistance is EMB. Because of the strong synergistic benefits of ethambutol when combined with other drugs, it is also frequently utilized to create regimens for drug-resistant tuberculosis (Zhu *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2020). In the intense phase of tuberculosis treatment, the drug is usually prescribed as part of a four-drug regimen that also includes isoniazid, rifampicin, and pyrazinamide. It is alarming to note that more than 4 percent of clinical isolates of *M. tuberculosis* have been shown to be resistant to ethambutol. The *embCAB* gene locus, which is involved in the synthesis of the cell wall components arabinogalactan and lipoarabinomannan, is the main target of ethambutol (Telentiet *al.*, 1997). Most often, mutations in the *embB* gene—particularly the classic mutations at codons 306, 406, and 497—are linked to the emergence of ethambutol resistance (Zhao *et al.*, 2015). Changes in the *embB* gene, specifically in *embB* codon 306, also known as the ethambutol resistance determining region (ERDR), have been frequently linked to resistance to ethambutol. It has been thought that ERDR sequence analysis can quickly screen for ethambutol resistance. Nevertheless, isolates of *M. tuberculosis* that are sensitive to ethambutol have also been found to have mutations at these codons (Plinkeet *al.*, 2006). Concerns are raised regarding the clinical importance of ethambutol mutations for the development of ethambutol resistance due to the inconsistent results between phenotypic and genotypic resistance tests. Because of this, the molecular diagnostics for ethambutol susceptibility are considerably behind those for other anti-tuberculosis drugs, which present a significant obstacle to the development of an appropriate treatment strategy.

Conclusion

Treatment for tuberculosis clinical strains resistant to first-line tuberculosis regimens is more challenging than for drug-susceptible strains; it requires prolonged chemotherapy (up to two years of treatment), costly and toxic medications, and a higher risk of treatment failure and mortality. In conclusion, our review article contributes to the evaluation of the current knowledge regarding mutations linked to the drug-resistant *M. tuberculosis* complex.

Therefore, early identification of first-line drugs resistance in *M. tuberculosis* clinical isolates will have clear benefits for patients as well as the general public's health issues, as it will allow for early access to the right effective treatment and the prevention of drug-resistant strains of *M. tuberculosis* strains.

Funding

Not available

References

- Alangaden GJ, Kreiswirth BN, Aouad A, Khetarpal M, Igno FR, Moghazeh SL, Manavathu EK, Lerner SA.** 1998. Mechanism of resistance to amikacin and kanamycin in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **42**, 1295-1297. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.42.5.1295>.
- Bakuła Z, Napiórkowska A, Bielecki J, Augustynowicz-Kopec E, Zwolska Z, Jagielski T.** 2013. Mutations in the *embB* gene and their association with ethambutol resistance in multidrug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clinical isolates from Poland. *BioMed Research International* **2013**, 167954. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/167954>.
- Banerjee A, Dubnau E, Quemard A, Balasubramanian V, Um KS, Wilson T, Collins D, de Lisle G, Jacobs WR.** 1994. *inhA*, a gene encoding a target for isoniazid and ethionamide in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Science* **263**, 227-230. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.8284673>.

- Baulard AR, Betts JC, Engohang-Ndong J, Quan S, McAdam RA, Brennan PJ, Loch C, Besra GS.** 2000. Activation of the pro-drug ethionamide is regulated in mycobacteria. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **275**, 28326-28331. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M003744200>.
- Boshoff HI, Warner DF, Gold B.** 2023. Drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology* **13**, 1215294. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2023.1215294>.
- Bruning JB, Murillo AC, Chacon O, Barletta RG, Sacchetti JC.** 2011. Structure of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* D-alanine: D-alanine ligase, a target of the antituberculosis drug D-cycloserine. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **55**, 291-301. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.00558-10>.
- Bu Q, Qiang R, Fang L, Peng X, Zhang H, Cheng H.** 2023. Global trends in the incidence rates of MDR and XDR tuberculosis: findings from the global burden of disease study 2019. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* **14**, 1156249. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1156249>.
- Caceres NE, Harris NB, Wellehan JF, Feng Z, Kapur V, Barletta RG.** 1997. Overexpression of the D-alanine racemase gene confers resistance to D-cycloserine in *Mycobacterium smegmatis*. *Journal of Bacteriology* **179**, 5046-5055. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jb.179.16.5046-5055.1997>.
- Cohen KA, Stott KE, Munsamy V, Manson AL, Earl AM, Pym AS.** 2020. Evidence for expanding the role of streptomycin in the management of drug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **64**, 10-128. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.00860-20>.
- Comas I, Borrell S, Roetzer A, Rose G, Malla B, Kato-Maeda M, Galagan J, Niemann S, Gagneux S.** 2012. Whole-genome sequencing of rifampicin-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains identifies compensatory mutations in RNA polymerase genes. *Nature Genetics* **44**, 106. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.1038>.
- Dartois VA, Rubin EJ.** 2022. Anti-tuberculosis treatment strategies and drug development: challenges and priorities. *Nature Reviews Microbiology* **20**, 685-701. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-022-00731-y>.
- Dheda K, Gumbo T, Gandhi NR, Murray M, Theron G, Udwadia Z, Migliori GB, Warren R.** 2014. Global control of tuberculosis: from extensively drug-resistant to untreatable tuberculosis. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* **2**, 321-338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(14\)70031-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(14)70031-1).
- Farooqi JQ, Khan E, Alam SM, Ali A, Hasan Z, Hasan R.** 2012. Line probe assay for detection of rifampicin and isoniazid resistant tuberculosis in Pakistan. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association* **62**, 767.
- Fox HH. 1952. The chemical approach to the control of tuberculosis. *Science* **116**, 129-134. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.116.3006.129>.
- Gandhi NR, Nunn P, Dheda K, Schaaf HS, Zignol M, Van Soolingen D, Jensen P, Bayona J.** 2010. Multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis: a threat to global control of tuberculosis. *The Lancet* **375**, 1830-43. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)60410-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60410-2).
- Ginsburg AS, Woolwine SC, Hooper N, Benjamin Jr WH, Bishai WR, Dorman SE, Sterling TR.** 2003. The rapid development of fluoroquinolone resistance in *M. tuberculosis*. *New England Journal of Medicine* **349**, 1977-1978. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM200311133492023>.
- Hsu LY, Lai LY, Hsieh PF, Lin TL, Lin WH, Tasi HY, Lee WT, Jou R, Wang JT.** 2020. Two novel katG mutations conferring isoniazid resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Frontiers in Microbiology* **11**, 1644. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.01644>.

- Huang H, Zhang Y, Li S, Wang J, Chen J, Pan Z, Gan H.** 2018. Rifampicin resistance and multidrug-resistant tuberculosis detection using Xpert MTB/RIF in Wuhan, China: a retrospective study. *Microbial Drug Resistance* **24**, 675-679. <https://doi.org/10.1089/mdr.2017.0114>.
- Islam MM, Alam MS, Liu Z, Khatun MS, Yusuf B, Hameed HMA, Tian X, Chhotaray C, Basnet R, Abraha H, Zhang X, Khan SA, Fang C, Li C, Hasan S, Tan S, Zhong N, Hu J and Zhang T.** 2024. Molecular mechanisms of resistance and treatment efficacy of clofazimine and bedaquiline against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Frontiers in Medicine* **10**, 1304857. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2023.1304857>.
- Jagielski T, Bakula Z, Brzostek A, Minias A, Stachowiak R, Kalita J, Napiórkowska A, Augustynowicz-Kopeć E, Żaczek A, Vasiliauskiene E, Bielecki J.** 2018. Characterization of mutations conferring resistance to rifampin in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clinical strains. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy* **62**, 10-128. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.01093-18>.
- Jia H, Xu Y, Sun Z.** 2021. Analysis on Drug-Resistance-Associated Mutations among Multidrug-Resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Isolates in China. *Antibiotics* **10**, 1367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics10111367>.
- Johansen SK, Maus CE, Plikaytis BB, Douthwaite S.** 2006. Capreomycin binds across the ribosomal subunit interface using *thyA*-encoded 2'-O-methylations in 16S and 23S rRNAs. *Molecular Cell* **23**, 173-182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcel.2006.05.044>.
- Kandler JL, Mercante AD, Dalton TL, Ezewudo MN, Cowan LS, Burns SP, Metchock B, Cegielski P, Posey JE.** 2018. Validation of novel *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isoniazid resistance mutations not detectable by common molecular tests. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **62**, 10-128. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.00974-18>. [10.1128/AAC.00974-18](https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.00974-18).
- Khan AS, Phelan JE, Khan MT, Ali S, Qasim M, Mohammad N, Napier G, Ahmad S, Alam J, Khattak B, Campino S.** 2023. Genetic mutations underlying isoniazid-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Tuberculosis* **138**, 102286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tube.2022.102286>.
- Kiepiela P, Bishop KS, Smith AN, Roux L, York DF.** 2000. Genomic mutations in the *katG*, *inhA* and *aphC* genes are useful for the prediction of isoniazid resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from Kwazulu Natal, South Africa. *Tubercle and Lung Disease* **80**, 47-56. <https://doi.org/10.1054/tuld.1999.0231>.
- Lai C, Xu J, Tozawa Y, Okamoto-Hosoya Y, Yao X, Ochi K.** 2002. Genetic and physiological characterization of *rpoB* mutations that activate antibiotic production in *Streptomyces lividans*. *Microbiology* **148**, 3365-3373. <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-148-11-3365>.
- Lei B, Wei CJ, Tu SC.** 2000. Action mechanism of antitubercular isoniazid Activation by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* KatG, isolation, and characterization of InhA inhibitor. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **275**, 2520-2526. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.275.4.2520>.
- Maus CE, Plikaytis BB, Shinnick TM.** 2005. Molecular analysis of cross-resistance to capreomycin, kanamycin, amikacin, and viomycin in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **49**, 3192-7. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.49.8.3192-3197.2005>.
- Mdluli K, Slayden RA, Zhu Y, Ramaswamy S, Pan X, Mead D, Crane DD, Musser JM, Barry CE.** 1998. Inhibition of a *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* β -ketoacyl ACP synthase by isoniazid. *Science* **280**, 1607-1610. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.280.5369.1607>.

- Miggiano R, Rizzi M, Ferraris DM.** 2020. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* pathogenesis, infection prevention and treatment. *Pathogens* **9**, 385.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9050385>.
- Milano A, Pasca MR, Provvedi R, Lucarelli AP, Manina G, Ribeiro AL, Manganelli R, Riccardi G.** 2009. Azole resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is mediated by the MmpS5–MmpL5 efflux system. *Tuberculosis* **89**, 84-90.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tube.2008.08.003>.
- Mitchison DA.** 1985. The action of antituberculosis drugs in short-course chemotherapy. *Tubercle* **66**, 219-225.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0041-3879\(85\)90040-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0041-3879(85)90040-6).
- Mok S, Roycroft E, Flanagan PR, Montgomery L, Borroni E, Rogers TR, Fitzgibbon MM.** 2021. Overcoming the challenges of pyrazinamide susceptibility testing in clinical *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **65**, 10-128.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02617-20>.
- Nahid P, Mase SR, Migliori GB, Sotgiu G, Bothamley GH, Brozek JL, Cattamanchi A, Cegielski JP, Chen L, Daley CL, Dalton TL.** 2019. Treatment of drug-resistant tuberculosis. An official ATS/CDC/ERS/IDSA clinical practice guideline. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine* **200**, e93-142.
<https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201909-1874ST>.
- Nair J, Rouse DA, Bai GH, Morris SL.** 1993. The *rpsL* gene and streptomycin resistance in single and multiple drug-resistant strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Molecular Microbiology* **10**, 521-752.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2958.1993.tb00924.x>.
- Okamoto S, Tamaru A, Nakajima C, Nishimura K, Tanaka Y, Tokuyama S, Suzuki Y, Ochi K.** 2007. Loss of a conserved 7-methylguanosine modification in 16S rRNA confers low-level streptomycin resistance in bacteria. *Molecular Microbiology* **63**, 1096-1106.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2958.2006.05585.x>.
- Parish T, Roberts G, Laval F, Schaeffer M, Daffé M, Duncan K.** 2007. Functional complementation of the essential gene *fabG1* of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* by *Mycobacterium smegmatis fabG* but not *Escherichia coli fabG*. *Journal of Bacteriology* **189**, 3721-3728.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/JB.01740-06>.
- Plinke C, Rusch-Gerdes S, Niemann S.** 2006. Significance of mutations in embB codon 306 for prediction of ethambutol resistance in clinical *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* **50**, 1900-1902.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.50.5.1900-1902.2006>.
- Prasad R, Gupta N, Banka A.** 2018. Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis/rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis: Principles of management. *Lung India* **35**, 78-81.
https://doi.org/10.4103/lungindia.lungindia_98_17.
- Reeves AZ, Campbell PJ, Sultana R, Malik S, Murray M, Plikaytis BB, Shinnick TM, Posey JE.** 2013. Aminoglycoside cross-resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* due to mutations in the 5' untranslated region of *whiB7*. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **57**, 1857-1865.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02191-12>.
- Rengarajan J, Sasseti CM, Naroditskaya V, Sloutsky A, Bloom BR, Rubin EJ.** 2004. The folate pathway is a target for resistance to the drug para-aminosalicylic acid (PAS) in mycobacteria. *Molecular Microbiology* **53**, 275-282.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2958.2004.04120.x>.
- Rodríguez-García Á, Mares-Alejandre RE, Muñoz-Muñoz PL, Ruvalcaba-Ruiz S, González-Sánchez RA, Bernáldez-Sarabia J, Meléndez-López SG, Licea-Navarro AF, Ramos-Ibarra MA.** 2021. Molecular analysis of Streptomycin resistance genes in clinical strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and biocomputational analysis of the Mt GidB L101F variant. *Antibiotics* **10**, 807.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics10070807>.

Safi H, Lingaraju S, Amin A, Kim S, Jones M, Holmes M, McNeil M, Peterson SN, Chatterjee D, Fleischmann R, Alland D. 2013. Evolution of high-level ethambutol-resistant tuberculosis through interacting mutations in decaprenylphosphoryl- β -D-arabinose biosynthetic and utilization pathway genes. *Nature Genetics* **45**, 1190.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.2743>.

Saier Jr MH, Yen MR, Noto K, Tamang DG, Elkan C. 2008. The transporter classification database: recent advances. *Nucleic Acids Research* **37**, D274-8.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkn862>

Scorpio A, Zhang Y. 1996. Mutations in *pncA*, a gene encoding pyrazinamidase/nicotinamidase, cause resistance to the antituberculous drug pyrazinamide in tubercle bacillus. *Nature Medicine* **2**, 662.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/nm0696-662>.

Shafipour M, Shirzad-Aski H, Mohammadzadeh A, Ghazvini K, Zamani S, Koochi PM, Ghaemi S, Ghaemi EA. 2022. Evaluation of mutations related to streptomycin resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clinical isolates. *Current Microbiology* **79**, 343.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-022-03043-9>.

Shi D, Li L, Zhao Y, Jia Q, Li H, Coulter C, Jin Q, Zhu G. 2011. Characteristics of *embB* mutations in multidrug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates in Henan, China. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* **66**, 2240-2247.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkr284>.

Sinha P, Srivastava GN, Tripathi R, Mishra MN, Anupurba S. 2020. Detection of mutations in the *rpoB* gene of rifampicin-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains inhibiting wild type probe hybridization in the MTBDR plus assay by DNA sequencing directly from clinical specimens. *BMC Microbiology* **20**, 1-8.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-020-01967-5>.

Stemkens R, Jager VD, Dawson R, Diacon AH, Narunsky K, Padayachee SD, Boeree MJ, van Beek SW, Colbers A, Coenen MJ, Svensson EM. 2023. Drug interaction potential of high-dose rifampicin in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **67**, e00683-23.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.00683-23>.

Telenti A, Philipp WJ, Sreevatsan S, Bernasconi C, Stockbauer KE, Wieles B, Musser JM, Jacobs Jr WR. 1997. The *emb* operon, a gene cluster of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* involved in resistance to ethambutol. *Nature Medicine* **3**, 567-570.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/nm0597-567>.

Telenti A. 1997. Genetics of drug resistance in tuberculosis. *Clinics in Chest Medicine* **18**, 55-64.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-5231\(05\)70355-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-5231(05)70355-5).

Vilchèze C, Jacobs Jr WR. 2014. Resistance to isoniazid and ethionamide in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*: genes, mutations, and causalities. *Microbiology Spectrum* **2**, 431-453.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.MGM2-0014-2013>.

Waller NJ, Cheung CY, Cook GM, McNeil MB. 2023. The evolution of antibiotic resistance is associated with collateral drug phenotypes in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Nature Communications* **14**, 1517.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37184-7>.

Wang J, Zhao W, Liu R, Huo F, Dong L, Xue Y, Wang Y, Xue Z, Ma L, Pang Y. 2020. Rapid Detection of Ethambutol-Resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* from Sputum by High-Resolution Melting Analysis in Beijing, China. *Infection and Drug Resistance* **20**, 3707-3713.

<https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S270542>.

- Wang Z, Tang Z, Heidari H, Molaeipour L, Ghanavati R, Kazemian H, Koohsar F, Kouhsari E. 2023. Global status of phenotypic pyrazinamide resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clinical isolates: an updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Chemotherapy* **35**, 583-595.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1120009X.2023.2214473>.
- Wilson TM, Collins DM. 1996. *ahpC*, a gene involved in isoniazid resistance of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. *Molecular Microbiology* **19**, 1025-1034.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2958.1996.449980.x>.
- WHO, World Health Organization. **Global tuberculosis report**, 2022. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization 2022. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240061729> (Accessed January 20, 2024).
- Xu G, Liu H, Jia X, Wang X, Xu P. 2021. Mechanisms and detection methods of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* rifampicin resistance: the phenomenon of drug resistance is complex. *Tuberculosis* **128**, 102083.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tube.2021.102083>.
- Zaczek A, Brzostek A, Augustynowicz-Kopec E, Zwolska Z, Dziadek J. 2009. Genetic evaluation of relationship between mutations in *rpoB* and resistance of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* to rifampin. *BMC Microbiology* **9**, 1-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2180-9-10>.
- Zaw MT, Emran NA, Lin Z. 2018. Mutations inside rifampicin-resistance determining region of *rpoB* gene associated with rifampicin-resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Journal of Infection and Public Health* **11**, 605-610.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2018.04.005>.
- Zeng MC, Jia QJ, Tang LM. 2021. *rpoB* gene mutations in rifampin-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from rural areas of Zhejiang, China. *Journal of International Medical Research* **49**, 0300060521997596.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0300060521997596>.
- Zenteno-Cuevas R, Cuevas-Córdoba B, Parissi-Crivelli A. 2019. *rpoB*, *katG* and *inhA* mutations in multi-drug resistant strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* clinical isolates from southeast Mexico. *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica* **37**, 307-313.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eimc.2018.09.002>.
- Zhang M, Yue J, Yang YP, Zhang HM, Lei JQ, Jin RL, Zhang XL, Wang HH. 2005. Detection of mutations associated with isoniazid resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from China. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* **43**, 5477-5482.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.43.11.5477-5482.2005>.
- Zhang S, Chen J, Shi W, Liu W, Zhang W, Zhang Y. 2013. Mutations in *panD* encoding aspartate decarboxylase are associated with pyrazinamide resistance in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Emerging Microbes and Infections* **2**, e34.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/emi.2013.38>.
- Zhang X, Liu L, Zhang Y, Dai G, Huang H, Jin Q. 2015. Genetic determinants involved in p-aminosalicylic acid resistance in clinical isolates from tuberculosis patients in northern China from 2006 to 2012. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **59**, 1320-1324.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.03695-14>.
- Zhang Y, Heym B, Allen B, Young D, Cole S. 1992. The catalase-peroxidase gene and isoniazid resistance of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Nature* **358**, 591-593.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/358591a0>.
- Zhao LL, Sun Q, Liu HC, Wu XC, Xiao TY, Zhao XQ, Li GL, Jiang Y, Zeng CY, Wan KL. 2015. Analysis of *embCAB* mutations associated with ethambutol resistance in multidrug-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from China. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* **59**, 2045-2050.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.04933-14>.

Zhu C, Liu Y, Hu L, Yang M, He ZG. 2018. Molecular mechanism of the synergistic activity of ethambutol and isoniazid against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **293**, 16741–16750.

<https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.RA118.002693>.